

Numerical diffusion control for high and low diffusion numerical schemes with application to three dimensional flow

Amit Sachdeva
Vikram Sarabhai Space Centre (VSSC/ISRO)
(amit_sachdeva@vssc.gov.in)

ABSTRACT

Appropriate amount of numerical diffusion is essential for a compressible flow numerical scheme from the point of view of stability as well as quality of the results. In the present work, a diffusion regulation mechanism developed by Rao and Jaisankar is used for improving the shock capturing of some of the conventional compressible flow solvers. Direct application of the this method to schemes like Roe results in diverged solution due to very low numerical diffusion, which is not sufficient to stabilize the scheme. Numerical experiments are carried out to select an appropriate form of diffusion regulation parameter for its successful application to the second order Roe scheme. Application of this diffusion regulation mechanism is also demonstrated for three dimensional flow with Local Lax-Friedrichs as well as Roe scheme in the present work.

Key Words: Euler equations, Numerical diffusion, Roe scheme, LLF

NOMENCLATURE

F_I = Interface flux

F_i, F_j = Left and right state fluxes

D_I = Numerical diffusion

U = Vector of conservative variables

M = Mach number

δ = User defined parameter

ϕ_{DR} = Diffusion regulation parameter

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerical diffusion is an inherent feature of the compressible flow solvers. Excessive numerical diffusion in a numerical scheme may lead to smeared shock waves and contact discontinuities (they will be spreading to many grid points). On the other hand, lower numerical diffusion may lead to convergence problems and unphysical solutions like expansion shock etc. Many schemes like Roe scheme gives

excellent shock and discontinuity capturing when they are aligned with grid in multidimensional (2D and 3D) flows but results in diffused shocks and discontinuities when not aligned with the computational grid. One way to deal with this issue is to use multidimensional schemes, where Riemann problem is solved in dominant wave (like shock wave) aligned frame. Also there are schemes which make use of multidimensional information [Ref-1, 2] to improve the quality of the solution. But most of these schemes involve more computations and suffer with convergence problems.

A method for controlling the numerical diffusion was developed by Jaisankar and Rao [Ref-3]. Here numerical diffusion in the interface flux computation is multiplied by a diffusion regulation parameter (DR) to control its amount based on the local flow conditions. This method shows interesting results for highly diffusive schemes like LLF (Local Lax-Friedrichs) and Kinetic scheme. Direct use of DR (with exponential term) to second order accurate low diffusion schemes like Roe leads to convergence problems. In this work, numerical experiments are carried out to assess the appropriate usage of DR parameter for second order accurate solution with low diffusion schemes. Its application is also presented to three dimensional flow over ONERA M6 wing (earlier works presented applications to 1D and 2D flows only).

2. Diffusion Regulation Parameter

For carrying out this work, SU² (Stanford University Unstructured) code has been used [Ref-4]. It is an open source code under active development at Stanford University. It can handle variety of fluid dynamics problems (compressible, incompressible,

*Scientist, Aerodynamic Data Synthesis Division, VSSC

moving bodies etc). SU² also provides adjoint methods to solve the aerodynamic shape optimization problems. One can easily modify the existing subroutines or write new subroutines in the code to carry out research work.

SU² uses Finite Volume Method (FVM) with median-dual scheme to solve Navier-Stokes and Euler equations. Implicit, explicit and dual time stepping procedures are available for handling various types of time dependent problems.

For all the problems in this work, implicit time stepping is used. MUSCL reconstruction with Venkatakrishnan limiter is applied to achieve the second order accuracy. SU² supports various boundary conditions for both internal as well as external flows.

Numerical schemes for solving compressible flow problems has inbuilt numerical diffusion. This numerical diffusion varies from scheme to scheme. Some of the schemes like LLF [Ref-5] has high amount of numerical diffusion, which causes smearing of shock and contact discontinuity to many grid points. Jaisanskar and Rao [Ref-3] proposed a diffusion regulation mechanism to control the amount of numerical diffusion in a scheme.

For many schemes, interface flux can be written as average of left and right state fluxes with a numerical diffusion term.

$$F_I = \frac{1}{2}(F_i + F_j) - D_I \quad -- (1)$$

Numerical diffusion term D_I for some of the schemes can be written as –

$$D_I = \alpha \Delta U \quad -- (2)$$

Here ΔU is difference of right and left state conservative variable. Parameter α depends on the numerical scheme. This numerical diffusion term varies from scheme to scheme. One simplest such scheme is LLF scheme. In this scheme, α is spectral radius of the flux jacobian matrix. For Roe scheme, diffusion term \mathbf{D} uses Roe matrix obtained by Roe averaged variables.

For schemes like LLF and Roe, diffusion regulation parameter (DR) can be directly applied to the interface flux by multiplying it with numerical diffusion term –

$$F_I = \frac{1}{2}(F_i + F_j) - \Phi_{DR} D_I \quad -- (3)$$

DR Parameter (Φ_{DR}) is based on the difference between left and right state Mach number across the interface.

It is defined as follows -

$$\Phi_{DR} = \frac{\Delta M^2 + \delta^2}{2\delta} (1 - e^{-kM_{mean}}) \text{ if } |\Delta M| \leq \delta$$

$$\Phi_{DR} = |\Delta M| \text{ if } \delta < |\Delta M| \leq 1.0$$

$$\Phi_{DR} = 1.0 \text{ if } |\Delta M| > 1.0$$

$$\Delta M = M_{Left} - M_{Right} \quad -- (4)$$

Value of diffusion regulation parameter varies with jump in Mach number across the interface.

Here M_{mean} is arithmetic average of left and right state Mach numbers. Parameters δ and k are user-defined parameters. Parameter δ takes the value between 0 and 1. In the earlier work [Ref-3], parameter k was determined by numerical experiments and its value was set to 10 for most of the problems.

3. Issues with diffusion regulation parameter with second order accurate solution

For highly diffusive schemes like LLF, diffusion regulation works well for the second order accurate solutions. However, for low diffusion schemes like Roe, its direct application (with exponential term) leads to unstable solution. It is due to very small numerical diffusion resulting by the application of DR. This small numerical diffusion is not enough to have a stable scheme. Also for low diffusion scheme with second order accuracy, one cannot have significant reduction in numerical diffusion.

To apply it on low diffusion schemes for second order accuracy, a numerical experiment is carried out over NACA0012 airfoil for Mach number 0.85 and angle of attack 1°. Here shock forms over both windward and leeward surface of the airfoil. For second order accurate solution with Roe scheme, exponential term is removed and δ is varied such as diffusion reduces by minimum with factor of 1/2, 3/8, 1/4 or 1/8 times (corresponding $\delta=1, 3/4, 1/2$ and $1/4$ respectively) to maximum by factor of 1 (which corresponds to original scheme without DR) of the original schemes.

Here DR takes the form-

$$\Phi_{DR} = \frac{\Delta M^2 + \delta^2}{2\delta} \quad -- (5)$$

DR parameter in a problem (Φ_{DR}) varies from minimum $\delta/2$ (when $\Delta M=0$) to maximum 1 (when $|\Delta M|>1$).

Figure 1 Pressure contours over NACA-0012 airfoil

Figure 2 Cp distribution over airfoil (windward and leeward surface)

Figure 3 Zoomed view of location A in Figure 2

Figure 4 Zoomed view of location B in Figure 2

Figure 2 shows pressure distribution over windward and leeward surface of NACA 0012 airfoil. Figure 3 and 4 shows zoomed view of the location A and B (marked in Figure 2). One can clearly see that oscillations in the solution increases with decreasing value of δ (reduction in numerical diffusion) while original scheme gives monotonic solution. Figure 5 presents convergence history (density residual) with variation in value of δ . It can be observed that with reduction in value of δ , overall residual fall is lower and convergence is poorer.

Figure 5 Convergence with variation in δ parameter

Numerical experiments were carried out over ONERA M6 wing as well. Solutions blew out after certain number of iterations for cases having δ smaller than 1. Based on above numerical experiments, $\delta=1$ is used for all the second order accurate simulations for Roe scheme with application of DR parameter.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Ramp in a supersonic channel

To demonstrate the improvements in accuracy 15° ramp in a supersonic channel, simulations are carried out at Mach number 2.0. Here

oblique shock forms over the ramp and reflects from top and bottom wall of the channel. Results are presented for first and second order accurate solution with LLF and Roe schemes over 60×20 grid (Figure 6 and Figure 7).

Figure 6 Pressure contours 60×20 grid (First order results)

Figure 7 Pressure contours 60×20 grid (Second order results)

Results for all the first order accurate solution are highly diffusive. For 1st order accurate solution, significant improvement is seen for all the schemes with the application of DR for both Roe and LLF schemes. Here shocks are captured much more crisply and accurately with less numerical diffusion. For first order solution, DR is applied with exponential term.

For second order accurate solution, good results are obtained for LLF scheme with application of DR. For low diffusion schemes (Roe), DR is applied without exponential term and $\delta=1.0$ (eqn-5). Improvements can be seen for these schemes as well because shocks are comparably crisper with the application of DR.

4.2 Flow over ONERA-M6 wing

In earlier work [Ref -3], application of diffusion regulation was presented for 1D and 2D problems. In the present effort, its application is demonstrated for a 3D flow problem over ONERA-M6 wing. Inviscid flow simulations are carried out at transonic Mach number ($M=0.8395$, $\alpha=3.06^\circ$) over ONERA-M6 wing. Implicit time stepping is used for the time marching. Venkatakrisnan limiter is applied for the

second order accurate solution. In this problem, a lambda shock pattern forms over the leeward surface of the wing.

Figure 8 pressure contours over ONERA-M6 wing leeward surface with LLF and LLF-DR

$y/c=0.65$

$y/c=0.95$

Figure 9 C_p distribution over section $y/c=0.65$ and 0.95 respectively with LLF and LLF-DR

Figure 10 pressure contours over ONERA-M6 wing leeward surface with LLF and LLF-DR

Figure 11 C_p distribution over section $y/c=0.65$ and 0.95 respectively with Roe and Roe-DR

Figure 8 gives comparison between LLF and LLF with DR simulation results. LLF produces very diffusive results with highly smeared shocks. With application of DR, significant improvements are observed in the results and shocks are captured accurately with low numerical diffusion. Comparison of experimental data at sectional locations $y/c=0.65$ and 0.95 are shown in Figure 9. It can be observed that original LLF results depart considerably from the experimental results. This is again due to highly diffusive nature of the scheme. With application of DR, results are much more accurate and closer to the experimental results.

Improved results are obtained with the application of DR to Roe scheme as well. Here DR is applied without exponential term and $\delta=1.0$. Details are presented in Figure 10 & 11. Shocks are captured crisply in comparison to the solution with original schemes. Comparison of pressure data also shows improvements in prediction for the leading edge portion of the wing.

4. CONCLUSION

Application of Diffusion Regulation mechanism is demonstrated for LLF and Roe scheme with second order accurate solution for 2D and 3D flows. Numerical experiments are carried out to select the appropriate amount of numerical diffusion for second order accurate simulations with Roe scheme, which otherwise gives unstable solution with the original form of DR parameter. Comparison of the simulations results with experimental data shows very good improvements for LLF scheme with DR. Application of DR (without exponential term) to second order accurate Roe scheme also shows improvements in shock capturing over the original Roe scheme.

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